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Meta-analysis

The impact of the Mediterranean diet on alleviating depressive symptoms in adults: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials

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1 **Abstract**

2 **Context**

3 High adherence to the Mediterranean diet (MD) has been associated with a reduced risk of
4 depression in prospective cohort studies, but whether MD interventions are effective among
5 adults with depression is uncertain.

6 **Objective**

7 This study aimed to synthesize the effects of MD interventions on the severity of depressive
8 symptoms in adults with depression.

9 **Data Sources**

10 PubMed, Cochrane CENTRAL, PsycINFO, Scopus and Web of Science were systematically
11 searched from database inception to March 2023. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic
12 Review and Meta-Analyses guidelines and the Cochrane recommendations were followed.
13 Randomized controlled trials (RCTs) comparing MD interventions *vs.* control conditions in
14 adults with depressive disorders or depressive symptoms were included.

15 **Data Extraction**

16 Two authors extracted the data independently. The Sidik-Jonkman estimator, the I^2 metric, and
17 the prediction interval were used to estimate between-study heterogeneity. To determine the risk
18 of bias and certainty of evidence from RCTs, we used the Cochrane Collaboration's Risk of Bias
19 2 and Grades of Recommendation, Assessment, Development, and Evaluation tools,
20 respectively.

21 **Data Analysis**

22 In total, 1507 participants (mean age range: 22.0–53.3 years) with depression were initially
23 included in the five RCTs of this review. Compared to control conditions, MD interventions

24 significantly reduced depressive symptoms among young and middle-aged adults with major
25 depression or mild to moderate depressive symptoms (standardized mean difference: -0.53; 95%
26 confidence interval: -0.90 to -0.16; $I^2 = 87.1\%$). The prediction interval ranged from -1.86 to
27 0.81. The overall risk of bias was within the range of 'some concerns' to 'high', while the
28 certainty of evidence was low.

29 **Conclusion**

30 MD interventions appear to have substantial potential for alleviating depressive symptoms in
31 people experiencing major or mild depression. However, to establish robust recommendations,
32 there remains a need for high-quality, large-scale, and long-term RCTs.

33 **Systematic Review Registration**

34 PROSPERO registration number CRD42022341895.

35 **Keywords:** depressive disorder, diet therapy, healthy diet, mental health, mental disorders,
36 nutrition therapy, psychiatry.

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45 **INTRODUCTION**

46 Mental disorders were the seventh leading cause of disease burden worldwide in 2019.¹ Among
47 them, depressive disorders are the primary cause of disability burden from early adulthood to old
48 age,¹ affecting 279.6 million people with a lifetime prevalence ranging from 3.4 to 4.2%.²
49 Moreover, the elevated economic cost (estimated at US\$ 1 trillion per year from anxiety and
50 depressive disorders) highlights a considerable burden on global society.³ Epidemiological and
51 economic estimates are probably conservative, as the complex clinical picture of depression
52 leads to a high proportion of undiagnosed cases.⁴

53 Although substantial advances in research have demonstrated the efficacy of psychological
54 and pharmacological treatments for clinical depression,^{5,6} translation to real-world benefits
55 remains a global challenge, as not all individuals with depression achieve or sustain symptom
56 remission with standard treatment alone.^{7,8} Additionally, individuals with depressive symptoms
57 who do not meet the criteria for a diagnosis of depressive disorder (i.e., subthreshold or
58 subsyndromal depression) represent a challenge for clinical settings because few treatment
59 options are available.^{9,10} The multifactorial etiology and phenotypic heterogeneity of depression
60 are constant difficulties in treatment effectiveness.¹¹

61 In this context, lifestyle-based interventions have emerged as potential strategies in the
62 treatment of depression.¹² Specifically, a previous meta-analysis reported the benefits of dietary
63 interventions (i.e., all types of diets aimed at decreasing unhealthy food intake, improving
64 nutrient intake and/or restricting caloric intake) on reducing depressive symptoms in the general
65 adult population.¹³ Indeed, current evidence highlights whole food dietary interventions as a
66 powerful adjuvant strategy with a positive impact on the treatment of people with depression.¹⁴
67 Regarding specific dietary patterns, prospective cohort evidence provided convincing data that

68 both the Mediterranean diet (MD) and the dietary inflammatory index decrease the likelihood of
69 depression.¹⁵ For instance, these dietary indexes support the consumption of similar antioxidant-
70 rich food groups, such as fish, fruits, nuts, pulses, seeds, and vegetables.¹⁵ The MD prototype,
71 considered mainly a plant-based food matrix, could play a supportive antidepressant role¹⁶
72 through the synergistic effects of its food features (i.e., antioxidant and anti-inflammatory
73 properties).¹⁷ Moreover, the concept of MD might incorporate other lifestyle elements (e.g.,
74 physical activity, sleep)¹⁸ that could contribute to the nutritional benefits of this food model.¹⁹

75 Previous literature has tried to shed light on the relationship between MD and depressive
76 symptoms. A recent umbrella review of meta-analyses of observational studies supports an
77 association between high adherence to the MD and a lower risk of depression.¹⁵ However, the
78 majority of evidence in this field is based on longitudinal or cross-sectional studies in the general
79 population.¹⁵ Although evidence supporting the role of dietary interventions in mental health has
80 grown in the last decade,¹² there is limited evidence regarding the effects of MD interventions in
81 people suffering from depression.¹⁵ Thus, only a previous 2020 systematic review with a meta-
82 analysis of randomized controlled trials (RCTs, to 2019) has analyzed the effectiveness of diet
83 on clinical depression or depressive symptoms, reporting a nonsignificant reduction in symptom
84 severity; however, it focused on interventions of all types of diets.²⁰

85 In a preliminary search,²¹ new evidence on the effects of MD-focused strategies for the
86 treatment of depression was observed. In this sense, this review places the spotlight on
87 population subgroups (i.e., individuals suffering from depression) to provide specific dietary
88 recommendations (i.e., MD) that may ameliorate or manage depressive symptomatology.²² In
89 particular, the focus on nutritional psychiatry in this review will be helpful to aid in guiding

90 feasible and affordable nutritional interventions to maintain and improve mental health status in
91 individuals with depression.

92 Therefore, this study synthesized the available evidence from RCTs on the effects of MD
93 interventions on the severity of depressive symptoms in adults with depressive disorders or
94 depressive symptoms.

95 **METHODS**

96 This systematic review was performed in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for
97 Systematic Review and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 statement²³ (**Table S1** in the Supporting
98 Information online) and the Cochrane Collaboration Handbook for Systematic Reviews of
99 Interventions.²⁴ The study protocol was registered in PROSPERO (CRD42022341895) and
100 published elsewhere.²¹ Two researchers (BBP and VDG) independently performed the literature
101 search, screening, trial selection, data extraction, risk of bias, and certainty assessment, with any
102 disagreements resolved by a third researcher (AEM).

103 **Search Strategy and Eligibility Criteria**

104 Systematic searches were conducted in the following electronic databases from inception to
105 March 1, 2023: PubMed (from 1993), Cochrane CENTRAL (from 1993), PsycINFO (from
106 1999), Scopus (from 1980) and Web of Science (from 1993). Additional searches were
107 performed on trial registry data portals, i.e., the International Clinical Trials Registry Platform
108 and ClinicalTrials.gov. The complete search strategy for each database is detailed in **Table S2** in
109 the Supporting Information online.

110 The rationale for the eligibility criteria was performed using the patient, intervention,
111 comparison, outcome, and study design (PICO) framework²⁴ (**Table 1**). To be included, studies
112 retrieved from the peer-reviewed literature must report the following: (i) population: adults (≥ 18

113 years of age) with a clinical diagnosis of depressive disorder; in addition, studies that determined
114 the presence of depression through physicians or trained health professionals using a recognized
115 diagnostic schedule, self-report of current medical diagnosis or antidepressant treatment, or a
116 validated rating scale²⁵ to specify mild, moderate or severe depressive symptoms were included;
117 (ii) intervention: MD-only (e.g., dietary advice or instructions, therapy sessions, provision of
118 relevant Mediterranean foods, cooking workshops), combined (e.g., MD plus nutrient
119 supplements) or composite (e.g., MD as a component of a lifestyle program) interventions; (iii)
120 comparison: non-MD control group/condition, such as usual treatment for depression or habitual
121 diet; (iv) outcome: changes in the indicator of depressive symptoms severity for intervention and
122 control groups separately according to validated observer rating or self-rating scales;²⁵ and (iv)
123 study design: peer-reviewed RCTs. No language or publication date restrictions were applied.
124 Full details of the eligibility criteria are provided in **Table S3** in the Supporting Information
125 online.

126 **Data Collection and Analysis**

127 **Study Selection**

128 All identified studies were entered into the Rayyan reviewing system online,²⁶ and a three-step
129 process was applied: 1) duplicate articles were excluded; 2) based on the title and abstract,
130 studies that did not address the MD-depression relationship in participants with depression were
131 excluded; and 3) the remaining studies were analyzed by reading the full text to determine
132 whether they met the eligibility criteria.

133 **Data Extraction**

134 The following data were extracted from the included studies: 1) authors and year of publication;
135 2) country in which data were collected; 3) RCT design and length; 4) sample size; 5) participant

136 information (biological sex, age, body mass index, tobacco use, depressive status, antidepressant
137 use); 6) characteristics related to MD interventions (type, protocol, composition, compliance)
138 and comparison groups (type, protocol); 7) measures of depressive symptoms and MD adherence
139 (scales); 8) results in depressive symptom severity and MD adherence (*n*, pre–post mean and SD
140 from both the intervention and control groups at baseline and at the end of the follow-up period);
141 and 9) methodological quality characteristics, main limitations, and sources of funding.

142 **Risk of Bias Assessment**

143 The revised Cochrane Collaboration’s Risk of Bias 2 (RoB2) tool for RCTs was used to evaluate
144 the risk of bias according to five domains: randomization process, deviations from the intended
145 interventions, missing outcome data, measurement of the outcome, and selection of the reported
146 results.²⁷ Each of the five domains was graded as low risk of bias, some concerns, or high risk of
147 bias. The overall risk of bias for each RCT was classified as 'low risk of bias' when a low risk of
148 bias was determined for all domains; 'some concerns' when at least one domain was evaluated as
149 raising some concerns, but no single domain was assessed as having a high risk of bias; or 'high
150 risk of bias' when a high risk of bias was identified for at least one domain.

151 **Grading the quality of evidence**

152 The Grades of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluation (GRADE)
153 methodology was used to determine the certainty of the evidence.²⁸ The outcome (i.e., depressive
154 symptom severity) was rated as having high-, moderate, low-, or very low-quality evidence
155 based on the study design, the risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, and
156 publication bias.²⁸

157 **Measures of intervention effect**

158 The standardized mean differences (SMDs) and their 95% CIs for each study were calculated
159 using Cohen's d index.²⁹ Negative SMD values indicate a reduction in depressive symptoms in
160 favor of MD interventions. The criterion proposed by Cohen to classify the effect size estimator
161 (i.e., SMD) as small (SMD=0.2), medium (SMD=0.5) or large (SMD=0.8) was considered.²⁹

162 **Data Synthesis**

163 A meta-analysis was performed when at least five studies addressed the same outcome.³⁰ As
164 considerable between-study heterogeneity was expected, a random-effects model was used to
165 pool SMDs for the effects of MD interventions vs. control conditions on the severity of
166 depressive symptoms (between-group differences). The Sidik-Jonkman estimator was applied to
167 calculate the heterogeneity variance.³¹ Moreover, the prediction interval (PI) was reported to
168 present heterogeneity in the same metric as SMD and to reflect the variation in true treatment
169 effects to be expected in future studies, which aids clinical decision-making.³² Heterogeneity
170 across the RCTs was assessed using the I^2 metric, categorized as not important (0% – 40%),
171 moderate (30% – 60%), substantial (50% – 90%), or considerable (75 – 100%), and
172 corresponding p values were also considered.²⁴

173 Sensitivity analyses were conducted to control for uncertainty in the estimation of between-
174 study heterogeneity by applying Knapp-Hartung adjustments.³³ Moreover, the robustness of the
175 summary estimates was assessed using the leave-one-out method.²⁴ Additional analyses were
176 carried out by calculating the pooled SMD with studies that focused only on dietary
177 interventions,³⁴⁻³⁷ i.e., excluding lifestyle interventions,³⁸ to elucidate the direct impact of dietary
178 improvement on depressive states. Finally, pooled SMDs were calculated according to each
179 depressive symptom scale applied in those studies that used more than one^{34,37} to evaluate the
180 possible influence of each measuring instrument.

181 Statistical significance was set at a two-sided $p < 0.05$. All analyses were conducted using R
182 software (version 4.2.3; R Foundation for Statistical Computing) with the *meta* package.³⁹

183 **Methodological considerations**

184 In studies where more than one assessment was made throughout the follow-up,^{34–36,38} the data of
185 the longest follow-up duration was considered. When RCTs reported the severity of depressive
186 symptoms on more than one scale^{34,37} or compared more than one MD intervention group with
187 the same control condition,³⁸ the respective measures were combined with a random-effects
188 model to calculate a single SMD for each study. Furthermore, if the included studies presented
189 analyses according to adherence to intervention, the results of participants receiving an adequate
190 dose (i.e., a priori compliance threshold considered by each study representing a clinically
191 sufficient treatment dose as a minimum) were selected. This condition was observed in one
192 RCT.³⁴

193 **RESULTS**

194 **Study selection**

195 A total of 2304 studies were considered for title-abstract review after removing duplicates, of
196 which 31 were fully assessed for eligibility and 26 were finally excluded for various reasons
197 (**Table S4** in the Supporting Information online). Finally, five RCTs were included in this
198 systematic review and meta-analysis (**Figure S1** in the Supporting Information online).

199 **Study characteristics**

200 **Tables 1** and **S5–S7** in the Supporting Information online summarize the main characteristics
201 and results of the included studies. The RCTs were conducted between 2017³⁷ and 2022.^{36,38} The
202 clinical trials included young³⁶ and middle-aged adults.^{34,35,37,38} RCTs had a parallel^{35–38} or
203 factorial³⁴ design.

204 **Population**

205 Among the total sample of participants at baseline (n=1507, mean age range: 22.0–53.3 years,
206 72.1% women), 1120 adults from Mediterranean^{34,38} and non-Mediterranean countries^{34–37}
207 completed the follow-up assessments. The mean age of the participants ranged from 22.0³⁶ to
208 53.3³⁸ years. Participants included in RCTs had major depressive disorder (clinical diagnosis^{35–37}
209 or self-reported³⁵) or mild to moderate depressive symptoms (self-reported³⁴ or suspected
210 depression according to general practitioner and scale administered by trained
211 interviewers³⁸). Three RCTs included individuals with poor self-reported diet quality.^{35–37} In all
212 RCTs, the participants were randomly assigned to the intervention and control groups at baseline
213 and had similar adherence to the MD and severity of depressive symptoms.^{34–38} Most RCTs
214 included individuals with and without pharmacological treatment^{35–38} or receiving professional
215 psychological treatment^{35–37} One study analyzed participants with specific health conditions
216 other than depression, including overweight or obesity.³⁴

217 **Mediterranean diet interventions**

218 All included RCTs considered MD interventions focused on nutrition education, i.e., advice to
219 change dietary habits toward an MD style and improve food-related behavior.^{34–38} The
220 intervention duration ranged from 6 to 48 weeks. Studies used one³⁸ or multiple^{34–37} MD
221 intervention modalities, such as individual^{34,36,37} (e.g., motivational interviews, personalized
222 goals) or group^{34,35,38} (e.g., behavior activation, cooking workshops) face-to-face sessions,
223 supply of food hampers, and supporting information (e.g., meal plans, recipe ideas, shopping
224 lists).^{35–37} MD-only,^{36,37} combined^{34,35} (i.e., MD plus nutrient supplementation) and composite³⁸
225 (i.e., MD as an element of a lifestyle program that includes psychoeducation, behavior activation,
226 sleep hygiene habits and physical activity) interventions were performed. Dietitians,^{34,35,37}

227 nutritionists,^{35,36} and psychologists^{34,38} conducted MD interventions. Participants' compliance
228 with MD interventions was assessed by monitoring the face-to-face sessions,^{34,38} and one study
229 defined a priori good adherence to the intervention (i.e., ≥ 8 of the 21 sessions).³⁴ Moreover, one
230 RCT needed that all participants attend all appointments to complete the trial.³⁶ At the end of
231 follow-up, the intervention groups showed improved adherence to the MD according to self-
232 report questionnaires measuring diet quality compared to the control groups.³⁴⁻³⁸

233 **Control conditions**

234 The comparison groups were those with interactive (i.e., befriending support sessions or social
235 group)³⁵⁻³⁷ or noninteractive (i.e., habitual diet, placebo, multinutrient supplements, or general
236 medical care)^{34,38} control conditions.

237 **Outcome: Depressive symptoms**

238 The severity of depressive symptoms was measured using standardized scales administered by
239 trained interviewers³⁷ (i.e., Montgomery–Asberg Depression Rating Scale diagnostic interview)
240 or self-administered scales³⁴⁻³⁸ (i.e., Beck Depression Inventory Scale–version II, Depression
241 Anxiety and Stress Scale–21, Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale–Depression subscale,
242 Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology, and Patient Health Questionnaire–9).

243 **Risk of bias assessment**

244 According to the RoB2 tool,²⁷ the overall risk of bias in the included studies was rated 'some
245 concerns' in three studies^{34,36,38} and 'high risk' in two studies^{35,37} (**Figure S2A** in the Supporting
246 Information online). The two domains where most of the RCTs lacked information were
247 deviations from the intended interventions and measurement of the outcome (**Figure S2B** in the
248 Supporting Information online).

249 **Quality of evidence**

250 The GRADE assessment²⁸ shows a low quality of the evidence, caused by the risk of bias and
251 inconsistency. Full details are provided in **Table S8** in the Supporting Information online.

252 **Meta-analysis**

253 A significant moderate effect diminishing the severity of depressive symptoms was shown in
254 favor of MD interventions when compared to control conditions (SMD: -0.53 [95% CI: -0.90 to -
255 0.16]) (**Figure 1**). Considerable between-study heterogeneity was observed ($I^2 = 87.1\%$ [95% CI:
256 72.2 to 94.0], $p < 0.001$). The PI ranged from -1.86 to 0.81, indicating the 95% range of expected
257 treatment effects in future similar studies.

258 **Sensitivity analyses**

259 The results of the sensitivity analyses were consistent with the main results (**Figures S3–S5** and
260 **Table S9** in the Supporting Information online). The moderate effect remained significant after
261 applying the Knapp-Hartung adjustment (SMD: -0.53 [95% CI: -1.05 to -0.004]) (**Figure S3** in
262 the Supporting Information online). In turn, the pooled estimates were not modified when
263 removing each study one by one (**Figure S4** in the Supporting Information online). Moreover,
264 the pooled SMDs with studies that focused only on dietary interventions^{34–37} (i.e., MD-only and
265 MD combined) showed a significant moderate effect on reducing the severity of depressive
266 symptoms (SMD: -0.53 [95% CI: -1.00 to -0.05]) (**Figure S5** in the Supporting Information
267 online).

268 **DISCUSSION**

269 This systematic review with meta-analysis is the first to synthesize the evidence from RCTs
270 examining the effect of MD interventions on the severity of depressive symptoms in young and
271 middle-aged adults with major depression or mild to moderate depressive symptoms. The results
272 indicate that MD interventions are effective in treating depressive symptoms in this population.

273 Furthermore, sensitivity analyses confirmed the robustness of the main results. However, the
274 findings should be interpreted with caution because of the small number of RCTs, the
275 considerable between-study heterogeneity, the overall risk of bias of the included studies and the
276 low-certainty evidence for the proposed association.

277 The effectiveness of diet interventions in the control of depressive symptoms is a
278 controversial issue. Thus, while recent meta-analyses reported the beneficial effect of dietary
279 interventions in decreasing depressive symptoms in clinical (e.g., angina, breast cancer,
280 depression, type 2 diabetes) and nonclinical (depressive symptoms, healthy, obesity,
281 postmenopausal women) general adult populations,^{13,20} another meta-analysis showed
282 nonsignificant effects (Hedges' g : -0.27 [95% CI: -0.66 to 0.13]; $n=4$) of dietary interventions
283 (i.e., nutrition education based on US Department of Agriculture Food Pyramid, $n=2$; or MD
284 guidelines, $n=2$) on the reduction of depressive symptoms in adults with major depression or
285 depressive symptoms.²⁰ The present study, including RCTs focused only on MD strategies (i.e.,
286 dietary-only, combined, or composite intervention), supports a moderate effect (SMD: -0.53
287 [95% CI: -0.90 to -0.16]; $n=5$) of MD for relieving depressive symptomatology. The results
288 could represent a clinical impact of MD interventions according to a previous review that
289 established a preliminary estimated cutoff point (SMD: -0.24) of clinical relevance for
290 depression treatments based on the minimally significant difference from the patient's
291 perspective.⁴⁰ However, based on the PI value, negative effects of the intervention cannot be
292 ruled out for future studies, and more RCTs are needed to provide robust results.

293 Age is a crucial risk factor for depression that should be acknowledged. The last report from
294 the Global Burden of Disease in 2019 revealed that depressive disorders are ranked the 4th
295 leading cause of disability-adjusted life years from children to young adults and the 6th leading

296 cause for middle-aged adults.¹ Despite this, most of the evidence relies on cross-sectional and
297 observational data with adults free of depression;¹⁵ thus, RCTs are lacking, especially for seniors
298 (>70 years) and young adults (18–25 years) with depression. Indeed, four out of five RCTs
299 included in this review were conducted in middle-aged adults, and only one study was conducted
300 in young male adults (mean age: 22 years).³⁶ Recently, a prospective observational study (n=879
301 older adults; 3 years of follow-up) pointed out that MD adherence is negatively associated with
302 depression regardless of cognitive status.⁴¹ However, it should be considered that conducting a
303 large RCT with older adults suffering from depression could be challenging due to the
304 comorbidities associated and interrelated with increased age and depressive disorder, such as
305 multiple drug use, functional disabilities, and cognitive impairments. Moreover, regarding young
306 adults, MD is suggested as an effective adjunctive treatment for reducing depressive symptoms
307 in males with depression.⁴² Nevertheless, considering the specific characteristics of the young
308 adult population (e.g., short food preparation time, poor diet quality, socioeconomic barriers,
309 social media influence) and the challenge of adhering to a healthy diet,⁴³ it would be useful for
310 MD-based interventions to provide nutrition education that considers not excessive cooking time
311 and diet cost, ease preparation of dishes and recipes, and healthy online food options.⁴⁴

312 Apart from age, sex is a well-established risk factor for depression, with depressive disorders
313 being more common in females than males.^{1,13} Although the studies included in this review were
314 conducted in mixed populations, in four out of five, the percentage of females was >75%, with
315 only one study conducted in young male adults.³⁶ Some explanations could explain the higher
316 prevalence of depression in females compared to males. For example, males tend to underreport
317 depression.⁴⁵ Additionally, biological (i.e., hormonal, metabolism, and body composition) and
318 sociocultural sex differences should be considered⁴⁶ to explore the impact of MD interventions in

319 males and females with depression. Consequently, further RCTs are needed in specific
320 populations with depression, such as young and senior adults. Moreover, stratifying results by
321 age and sex might be recommended to provide more precise conclusions.

322 Different mechanisms have been proposed to explain the interplay between healthy dietary
323 patterns such as MD and depression.⁴⁷ Specifically, MD provides a rich source of bioactive
324 compounds (e.g., carotenoids, phytosterols, polyphenols, omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins), dietary
325 fiber (i.e., especially from fruits and vegetables) and trace elements (e.g., selenium, zinc) with
326 strong antioxidant properties^{48,49} that can affect the main biological mechanisms (i.e., oxidative
327 stress and pro-inflammatory state) of depression.^{47,50} Other possible pathways that could be
328 beneficially modulated by MD include brain-derived neurotrophic factor (i.e., related to synaptic
329 plasticity and neuronal survival and differentiation),⁵¹ endothelial function (i.e., higher
330 percentage of flow-mediated dilatation),⁵² gut microbiota (i.e., modulation of taxonomic
331 composition and short-chain fatty acid production),⁵³ and lipid metabolism (i.e., improved
332 triglyceride content of high-density lipoproteins).⁵⁴ Recently, the gut microbiota has emerged as
333 a key component in the connection between diet and depression.⁴⁷ The gut microbiota is
334 implicated in several physiological processes that influence cognitive function, neuropsychiatric
335 disorders, and behavior via the microbiota-gut-brain axis.⁵⁵ A healthy dietary pattern such as MD
336 could play a pivotal role in shaping gut microbiota diversity, function, and composition due to its
337 rich content of fiber, unsaturated fatty acids, and plant-based bioactive compounds.^{56,57} In this
338 sense, MD interventions could have a beneficial impact on the gut microbiome but also in
339 reducing oxidative stress and the chronic-low grade inflammatory status related to
340 depression.^{47,58}

341 Finally, the Mediterranean dietary pattern has been strongly associated with several beneficial
342 health outcomes^{59,60} and could encompass different lifestyle elements (e.g., adequate rest,
343 conviviality, regular physical activity)¹⁸ that contribute to reducing the severity of depressive
344 symptoms.⁶¹ In this regard, the complex bidirectional relationship between mental (i.e.,
345 depressive disorders) and cardiometabolic health (i.e., obesity) should be considered^{62,63} MD
346 interventions would have a positive impact on the treatment of individuals with depression, but
347 the mechanism to understand this effect could be confounded by changes in body composition.¹⁴
348 There is evidence pointing to the psychological effects of weight loss through diet interventions,
349 such as improvements in perceived body image and quality of life.⁶⁴ Moreover, mental health
350 benefits after dietary interventions focusing on weight loss could be enhanced in overweight or
351 obese individuals⁶⁵ and in those who lost more weight.⁶⁶ In this review, most of the included
352 studies did not report the pre-post intervention weight change. Therefore, future studies of MD
353 interventions in adults with depression should control for baseline weight and weight change
354 throughout the intervention. Moreover, future RCTs that categorize subjects according to their
355 adiposity levels may elucidate the impact of body composition on the efficacy of MD
356 interventions to reduce the severity of depressive symptoms in adults with depression.

357 Some study limitations must be acknowledged. First, the indicators showed considerable
358 between-study heterogeneity in the pooled estimates. Discrepancies in the characteristics of
359 participants, intervention and control condition protocols could lead to inconsistencies and bias
360 in the study relationship. Second, most studies included participants undergoing traditional
361 treatments for depression; therefore, the possibility of their influence in reducing the severity of
362 depressive symptoms cannot be ruled out. Third, most studies collected information on MD
363 adherence and symptomatology of depression through self-report questionnaires, which could be

364 susceptible to expectancy effects and present a certain degree of measurement errors due to recall
365 and information biases. Fourth, the number of included studies ($n < 10$) was inadequate to
366 perform meta-regressions or assess publication bias.^{24,67} Therefore, the findings of this review
367 should be considered with caution.

368 **CONCLUSIONS**

369 This systematic review with meta-analysis is the first to synthesize the effects of MD
370 interventions on the severity of depressive symptoms in adults with depression. The data suggest
371 that MD interventions can be effective in reducing depressive symptoms among young and
372 middle-aged adults with major depression or mild to moderate depressive symptoms, achieving
373 moderate significant relief compared to control conditions. This synthesis of RCTs provides the
374 highest level of evidence to consider MD interventions as a nutritional psychiatry approach for
375 individuals with major or mild depression. However, the results showed only low-certainty
376 evidence for the proposed association, highlighting the demand for more RCTs to strongly
377 support MD interventions in this population.

378

379 **Data sharing**

380 All necessary data supporting the conclusions of this article are available in the main manuscript
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399

400 **Supporting information**

401 **Table S1.** PRISMA checklist.

402 **Table S2.** Detailed information on search strategies.

403 **Table S3.** Full details of the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

404 **Table S4.** List of the studies fully assessed for eligibility and excluded.

405 **Table S5.** Protocols of the interventions and comparisons of the included studies.

406 **Table S6.** Methodological quality characteristics, limitations, and sources of funding of the
407 included studies.

408 **Table S7.** Main results of the included studies.

409 **Table S8.** GRADE assessment.

410 **Table S9.** Sensitivity analyses by not combining measures of depressive symptoms.

411 **Figure S1.** PRISMA flow diagram for identifying, screening, and determining the eligibility and
412 inclusion of studies.

413 **Figure S2.** Risk of bias of the randomized controlled trials included.

414 **Figure S3.** Sensitivity analysis using the Knapp-Hartung adjustment to calculate the confidence
415 interval around the pooled standardized mean difference.

416 Negative SMD values favored the MD intervention in reducing depressive symptoms among
417 adults with depression compared to control conditions. Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval;
418 MD, Mediterranean diet; SMD, standardized mean difference.

419 **Figure S4.** Sensitivity analysis by removing studies one by one from the pooled standardized
420 mean difference.

421 Negative SMD values favored the MD intervention in reducing depressive symptoms among
422 adults with depression compared to control conditions. Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval;
423 MD, Mediterranean diet; SMD, standardized mean difference.

424 **Figure S5.** Sensitivity analysis by pooling studies focused on dietary interventions only (i.e.,
425 excluding lifestyle interventions).

426 Negative SMD values favored the MD intervention in reducing depressive symptoms among
427 adults with depression compared to control conditions. Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval;
428 MD, Mediterranean diet; SMD, standardized mean difference.

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633 **TABLE AND FIGURE LEGENDS**

634 **Table 1.** PICO's criteria for inclusion of studies.

635 **Table 2.** Main characteristics of the studies included in the systematic review and meta-
636 analysis.

637 **Figure 1.** Pooled standardized mean difference for the effect of Mediterranean diet
638 interventions *vs.* control conditions on depressive symptom severity in young and middle-
639 aged adults with depression.

640 Legend Figure 1: Negative SMD values favored the MD intervention in reducing
641 depressive symptoms among adults with depression compared to control conditions. MD-
642 based interventions are defined as MD-only (e.g., dietary advice or instructions, therapy
643 sessions, provision of relevant Mediterranean foods, cooking workshops), combined (e.g.,
644 MD plus nutrient supplements) or composite (e.g., MD as a component of a lifestyle
645 program). Control conditions are defined as interactive (i.e., social group such as
646 befriending support sessions) or noninteractive (i.e., nonsocial group, such as usual
647 treatment for depression). Abbreviations: CI, confidence interval; MD, Mediterranean diet;
648 SMD, standardized mean difference.

Table 1.

Component	Criteria
Population	Adults (≥ 18 years of age) with depression or depressive symptoms
Intervention	Mediterranean diet interventions (i.e., only, combined, or composite)
Comparison	Control conditions without Mediterranean diet
Outcome	Depressive symptoms severity
Study design	Randomized controlled trials

Table 2.

Reference	Country	RCT design	Length (weeks)	<i>n</i> total	Women (%)	Age, y (mean ± SD)	BMI (kg/m ²)	Smoker (%)	Depressive status	AD use (%)	<i>n</i> int / con ¹	MD intervention ²		Comparison	DS severity (scale)
												Treatment mode	Other aspects		
Aguilar-Latorre et al. (2022) ³⁸	Spain	3-arm Parallel	6 ³	188	86.2	53.3 ± 13.1	n/r	n/r	Mild to moderate DS	71.3	37/49 42/49	LMP + group sessions LMP + group sessions	TAU TAU + WT	TAU	BDI-II
Bayes et al. (2022) ³⁶	Australia	2-arm Parallel	12	75	0	22.0 ± 2.7	n/r	16.7	MDD and moderate to severe DS	36.1	36/36	Food hamper + individual sessions + information	n/a	Befriending support sessions	BDI-II
Bot et al. (2019) ³⁴	Germany, Spain, UK, Netherlands	2x2 Factorial	48	1025	75.3	46.5 ± 5.4	31.4	18.0	Mild to moderate DS	0	198/196 191/194	FBAT + individual and group sessions	Placebo Multinutrient supplements	Placebo Multinutrient supplements	IDS, PHQ-9
Jacka et al. (2017) ³⁷	Australia	2-arm Parallel	12	67	71.6	40.3 ± 13.1	29.5	14.1	MDD and moderate to severe DS	68.7	31/25	Food hamper + individual sessions + information	n/a	Befriending support sessions	MADRS, HADS-D
Parletta et al. (2019) ³⁵	Australia	2-arm Parallel	12 ⁴	152	68.2	44.2 ± 13.0	n/r	n/r	MDD or moderate to severe DS	35.5	47/38	Food hamper + group sessions + information	Fish oil supplement	Social group	DASS-21

¹ Participants with available data at the final follow-up assessments (n posttreatment). ² All MD interventions focused on nutrition education (i.e., dietary advice and food-related habits). ³ Longitudinal follow-up 18 weeks after intervention.

⁴ Longitudinal follow-up 12 weeks after intervention.

AD, antidepressant use; BDI-II, Beck Depression Inventory Scale-version II; BMI, body mass index; con, control group; DASS-21, Depression Anxiety and Stress Scale-21; DS, depressive symptoms; FBAT, Food-related Behavioral Activation Therapy; HADS-D, Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale-Depression subscale; IDS, Inventory of Depressive Symptomatology; int, intervention; LMP, lifestyle modification program; MADRS, Montgomery-Asberg Depression Rating Scale; MD, Mediterranean diet; MDD, major depressive disorder; n/a, not applicable; n/r, not reported; PHQ-9, Patient Health Questionnaire 9; RCT, randomized controlled trial; TAU, treatment as usual; WT, wearable technology.